

reduction process. The value of $E_{1/2}$ shifted with increasing concentration of pyrazoles, revealing irreversible reduction. The reversibility of the waves was first tested with the help of log plots, and found to be irreversible⁸. The slow electron transfer behaviour of these compounds differing from the reversible nature for azobenzene⁹ under comparable conditions may be due to bulky pyrazole attached to the end of electroactive center¹⁰ (N=N group). The number of protons (Z_{H^+}) involved in the rate-determining step was calculated from the gradients of $E_{1/2}$ -pH and $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs E plots by the equation,

$$Z_{H^+} = \frac{E_{1/2}}{\text{pH}} = \frac{\alpha n_a}{0.0591} \quad (2)$$

The number of protons was found to be approximately one for all the compounds under investigation. Thus the number of electrons involved in the reduction is twice the number of protons consumed in the slow electron transfer step. Also from the slopes of $E_{1/2}$ -pH plots, the values of symmetry coefficient were evaluated (Table 1). Controlled potential electrolysis of the depolarizer at pH values 4.6 and 10.5 using the mercury pool cathode consumed 2 electrons.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) : The cyclic voltammograms of all compounds showed only one voltammetric cathodic peak at a HMDE between pH 4.2 and 11.2 containing 40% ethanol at 25° (concentration $1 \times 10^{-4} M$). Fig. 1 shows the cyclic voltammetric response of the parent pyrazole compound at a sweep rate (S) of 100 mV/s and pH 4.2. It also displays a digitally simulated curve for EC_{irrev} ¹¹. The plots of i_{pc} vs S and i_{pc} vs C were found to be straight-lines passing through the origin, indicating diffusion-controlled electrode process.

Fig. 1. Voltammograms for the reduction of the parent compound at a HMDE : (—) experimental, (---) theoretical; sweep rate 100 mV/s, pH = 4.2.

The evaluated kinetic parameters were tested by constructing theoretical current-potential curves via digital simulation method using the average electrochemical parameters. The excellent agreement between the observed experimental and computer generated ones provides a good indication that the CV wave can be completely described as EC_{irrev} ¹¹. The electrochemical parameters introduced to the EG & G Condesim package which allows accurate digital simulation for EC_{irrev} mechanism in cyclic voltammetry are : D (diffusion coefficient of the electroactive species), $E_{1/2}$ (half-wave potential), A (electrode area, $1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2$), C (bulk concentration, $1 \times 10^{-4} M$), k_s (heterogeneous rate constant for electron transfer), n_a (number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step), S (scan rate), α (symmetry coefficient), k_c (chemical rate constant). To establish the irreversible nature of the arylazopyrazole reduction process, quantitative criteria were employed.

Peak potentials (E_p) : According to Nicholson and Shain¹² for the EC_{irrev} process, the relationship (3) holds

$$E_p = \frac{2.303 RT}{2\alpha n_a F} \log v + \text{Constant} \quad (3)$$

Slopes > 30 mV per decade are predicted for totally irreversible waves. An experimental verification of eqn. (3) representing the plots of E_p vs $\ln v$ at given pH, is presented in Fig. 2. The results show the totally irreversible electron transfer process.

Fig. 2. The $E_p - \ln v$ relationship for the arylazopyrazoles at different pH : (+) *p*-Br, pH 11.2; (●) parent (H), pH 7.3; (×) *p*-Br, pH 7.3, (□) *p*-N(CH₃)₂, pH 4.2; (◇) parent (H), pH 4.2.

Evaluation of symmetry coefficients : Three independent methods were used to calculate the values of symmetry coefficients (Table 2) for the reduction process : (I) from the gradient of E_p vs $\log v$ as given in eqn. 3, (II) the slope of the relationship¹² between E_p vs $\log I_p$ for the irreversible

case is given by eqn. (4),

$$E_p = \frac{2.303 RT}{2\alpha n_a F} \log I_p + \text{Constant} \quad (4)$$

where I_p is the peak current, and (III) the breadth of the totally irreversible wave which depends on α according to eqn. (5)¹²,

$$E_p - E_{p/2} = 1.857 \frac{RT}{\alpha n_a F} \quad (5)$$

The symmetry coefficient values (Table 2) obtained by the three methods for irreversible systems are in excellent accord with each other and this confirms the EC_{irrev} mechanism.

Table 2. Convolution CV, CP, CC and digital simulation results

Compd	pH	$-E_p$ V	$D \times 10^5$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	α		
				E_p vs $\log v$	E_p vs $\log I_p$	$E_p - E_{p/2}$
Parent (H)	4.2	0.89	4.25 ^{a,b}	0.38	0.39	0.36
		0.88 ^b	4.21 ^c			
			4.23 ^d			
	7.3	0.95	4.12 ^{a,b}	0.41	0.40	0.39
		0.95 ^b	4.14 ^c			
			4.16 ^d			
11.2	1.15	3.94 ^{a,b}	0.37	0.34	0.36	
	1.13 ^b	3.97 ^c				
		3.95 ^d				
<i>p</i> -Br	4.2	0.77	4.31 ^{a,b}	0.33	0.32	0.35
		0.76 ^b	4.32 ^c			
			4.24 ^d			
	7.3	0.84	4.19 ^{a,b}	0.31	0.33	0.36
		0.85 ^b	4.20 ^c			
			4.12 ^d			
11.2	1.12	4.27 ^{a,b}	0.40	0.41	0.39	
	1.11 ^b	4.26 ^c				
		4.29 ^d				
<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	4.2	0.92	4.26 ^{a,b}	0.35	0.32	0.31
		0.91 ^b	4.28 ^c			
			4.29 ^d			
	7.3	1.03	4.14 ^{a,b}	0.36	0.40	0.41
		1.05 ^b	4.17 ^c			
			4.16 ^d			
11.2	1.19	4.31 ^{a,b}	0.35	0.37	0.34	
	1.20 ^b	4.32 ^c				
		4.24 ^d				

^aLimiting convoluted current ^bSimulation ^cChronocoulometry
^dChronopotentiometry

Calculation of the cyclic voltammetric waves : Computer generated cyclic voltammograms, assuming different values for the $E_{1/2}$ with the knowledge of k_s for electron transfer and symmetry coefficient (α) were used until the best fit was obtained with the experimental results. The theoretical curves which represents the EC_{irrev} mechanism¹¹ are in a good agreement with the background subtracted current-potential curve. This agreement supports the slow electron transfer rate followed by a fast chemical reaction, EC_{irrev} . The value of chemical rate constant, k_c (12 s) was found from simulation program (Condesim), which gives the best fit between the simulated and experimental voltammograms. In the case of EC_{irrev} mechanism, the following relationship can be used for the calculation of the heterogeneous rate constant (k_s) of the electron transfer process,

$$E_p = E^0 - \frac{RT}{\alpha n F} \left(0.78 - \frac{2.3}{2} \log \frac{\alpha n_a F D}{k_s} \right) - \frac{2.3 RT}{2\alpha n_a F} \log v \quad (6)$$

Table 3 shows that as the pH value increases, the value of k_s decreases. This probably indicates the slow electron transfer behavior for the depolarizers.

Table 3. Comparative results between computer generated and experimental data at sweep rate of 0.1 V/s

Compd	pH	k_s cm s^{-1}	$W_{1/2}$
Parent (H)	4.2	4.00×10^{-6a}	163 ^a
		4.32×10^{-6b}	171 ^b
	7.3	3.00×10^{-8a}	231 ^a
		3.05×10^{-8b}	235 ^b
	11.2	3.60×10^{-10a}	241 ^a
		3.67×10^{-10b}	247 ^b
<i>p</i> -Br	4.2	7.00×10^{-6a}	164 ^a
		7.80×10^{-6b}	173 ^b
	7.3	5.00×10^{-8a}	183 ^a
		5.78×10^{-8b}	191 ^b
	11.2	8.60×10^{-10a}	214 ^a
		8.67×10^{-10b}	209 ^b
<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	4.2	7.8×10^{-6a}	155 ^a
		7.87×10^{-6b}	169 ^b
	7.3	5.20×10^{-8a}	179 ^a
		5.24×10^{-8b}	184 ^b
	11.2	4.5×10^{-10a}	221 ^a
		4.56×10^{-10b}	225 ^b

^aComputer generated data ^bExperimental results

Convolution and deconvolution voltammetry : The basic concept of convolutive voltammetry is that the concentration of the reactant at the electrode surface, established by diffusion, can be calculated throughout the sweep applied. This enables us to use not only some particular points of a voltammetric curve such as E_p , $E_{p/2}$ (half-peak potential) and I_p (peak current) but the whole voltammogram. The convoluted current I_1 ^{13,14} of all the depolarizers does not return to zero at the end of cyclic sweeping with a clear gap between the sweep halves, supports EC_{irrev} ¹¹ mechanism of electrode reaction. Fig. 3 shows convoluted current for reduction of parent depolarizer at 0.1 V/s. The maximum convoluted current when the concentration of the de-

Fig. 3. Convolution (—) and deconvolution (-----) currents for reduction of the parent compound at a sweep rate of 0.1 V/s.

polarizer species at electrode surface equals zero can be expressed as¹³

$$I_{lim} = nFAD^{1/2}C \quad (7)$$

where I_{lim} is the limiting convoluted current in $A/s^{1/2}$, A the electrode area and other terms have their usual meanings. The diffusion coefficients of the arylazopyrazoles was evaluated using eqn. (7) and which agree well with other voltammetric techniques (Table 2).

Deconvoluted voltammetric data (dI_1/dt) for the parent depolarizers at 0.1 V/s show a voltammogram of unequal heights (Fig. 3) and the backward peak is much broader than forward peak. The deconvoluted current data confirm the presence of a fast chemical reaction followed the slow electron transfer process. The values of the half-peak width ($w_{1/2}$) (Table 3) are shifted from the values obtained for one reversible electron transfer (88.09 mV)^{13,14} and increase with increasing value of pH, which confirms the irreversible electron transfer process of the depolarizer species under consideration.

Chronoamperometry : Fig. 4 shows the chronoamperogram for the parent arylazopyrazole compound, obtained under similar conditions to the cyclic voltammetric experi-

Fig. 4. Chronoamperogram for the parent compound at pH = 7.5 and concentration = 1×10^{-4} M at HMDE.

ments at pH 7.5, but at more negative overpotentials. The slow rise in current at the beginning of the experiment may be due to a slight excess of damping. Chronocoulometry (CC) analysis has been used to estimate the diffusion coefficients for the depolarizers under consideration (Table 2). The straight-line relationship obtained by plotting charge (Q) vs time (t) as expressed in the equation¹⁵,

$$Q = \frac{2nFaCD^{1/2}t^{1/2}}{\pi^{1/2}} \quad (8)$$

allows us to evaluate the diffusion coefficient for the compounds under investigation (Table 2). The plot of $i\sqrt{t}$ vs time (Fig. 5) indicates that the results do not adhere to the Cottrell relationship¹⁶.

Fig. 5. Plot of $i\sqrt{t}$ vs t for the parent compound at pH = 7.5 and concentration = 1×10^{-4} M at HMDE.

Chronopotentiometry (CP) : Chronopotentiometric technique was performed on the depolarizers under consideration to determine the diffusion coefficient (*D*). Fig. 6 shows

Fig. 6. Chronopotentiogram for the parent compound at pH = 7.5 and concentration = 1×10^{-4} M at HMDE.

the profile of the chronopotentiometric data for the parent compound at pH 7.5, and displays one reduction transition time which has been analysed via equation (9)¹⁷,

$$I_{lim} = 2i_c (t_s/\pi)^{1/2} = nFAD^{1/2}C \quad (9)$$

where i_c is the polarization current and t_s the transition time of the investigated compound. The values obtained for the diffusion coefficient of the depolarizers under consideration (Table 2) from chronopotentiometric experiments were found to be in a good agreement with that obtained from dc polarography and convolution-deconvolution voltammetry.

Electrode reaction : According to the above discussion and interpretation of the electrochemical behaviour, the electrode process of the investigated compounds can be suggested to behave as protonation-deprotonation equilibrium followed by an EC_{irrev} mechanism. As the number of electrons involved in the reduction is two and the number of protons involved in the rate-determining step is one, and only one product is obtained after exhaustive electrolysis, then

The solution after coulometric analysis gave negative test for amino group, thereby showing that the reduction of $\text{N}=\text{N}$ stops to the hydrazo stage. The maximum absorbance at 320 nm disappears in solution after complete electrolysis. Furthermore, the above mentioned electrolysed solution does not give any polarographic wave or voltammetric response supporting the above electrode reaction. The above reaction mechanism is also supported by the work of others¹⁸.

Experimental

N-Benzylsulfonyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazole and its derivatives prepared by the literature method¹⁹ were purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol and their purity checked by elemental analysis and spectral data.

Stock solutions of the compounds were obtained using ethanol (A.R.) as a solvent. Solutions used for electrochemical studies were prepared by taking suitable volume of each stock solution to which the required quantity of the buffer solution and water were added to obtain the desired concentration in 40% ethanol (v/v). Britton-Robinson²⁰ buffers (pH 2.5–11.1) were prepared using analytical grade chemicals.

Polarograms were recorded on a Sargent-Welech 4001 polarograph. Triple-distilled mercury was used for the dme. The electrode capillary had the rate of 1.526 mg/s and a drop time of 3.5 s at $h = 60$ cm in 0.1 M KCl at zero applied potential. pH was measured on an Orion 201 pH-meter; Van Uitert and Hass²¹ method was applied for calibration of the pH-reading. Controlled potential electrolysis of the compound was carried out in buffered 40% ethanol (v/v) adjusted at the pH values 4.60 and 10.50, the measurements being conducted at the controlled potential of -0.7 and -1.0 V, respectively, vs SCE using an EG & G 173 potentiostat. An EG & G electrode assembly with a hanging mercury drop electrode (area = 1.2×10^{-6} cm²) as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and Pt-wire as a counter electrode were used during the electrochemical measurements. The spectra was measured using a Shimadzu 2100s instrument. The collection of electrochemical data for digital simulation was facilitated by use of EG & G CONDECON and CONDESIM softwares.

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